

Optically active terpolymer : Synthesis and characterization

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Limonene, an optically active terpene, has been polymerized with methyl acrylate and acrylonitrile by pyridiniumdicyanomethylide (PDMY) in dimethylformamide as radical initiator at 90° to yield optically active terpolymer. The kinetic parameters have been evaluated.

The synthesis of optically active polymers¹ has been a subject of keen interest. A search of literature reveals that polymers based on substituted and 1,1-disubstituted olefins do not give rise to optical activity unless optically active monomers or initiators are used.

The present communication highlights the synthesis of optically active terpolymers of methyl acrylate, acrylonitrile and limonene (an optically active terpene) using pyridinium dicyanomethylide as radical initiator².

Results and Discussion

The results of terpolymer synthesis are summarized in Table 1 and Fig. 1. It was observed that no homo- or copolymer was obtained for the following cases : (i) when limonene was subjected to homopolymerization in DMF using PDMY as initiator at 90° and (ii) when limonene was copolymerized with either acrylonitrile or with methyl acrylate using PDMY as initiator in DMF at 90°. However, when all the three monomers were subjected to polymerization together under the same conditions, terpolymers resulted.

Fig. 1. Plots of conversion (%) vs time (min), PDMY concentrations are (O) 3.4×10^{-3} , (Δ) 2.3×10^{-3} , (\bullet) 0.93×10^{-3} , (\square) 0.69×10^{-3} , (\otimes) 0.46×10^{-3} and (O) 0.23×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³; [MA] = 0.51 mol dm⁻³, [AN] = 1.26 mol dm⁻³, [LM] = 0.92 mol dm⁻³, temp = 90°

Table 1. Effect of reactant (initiator and monomers) concentration on rate of terpolymerization

Reactant $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	Percentage conversion	$R_p \times 10^5$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	$[\eta]$ dl g ⁻¹	Optical rotation
Temp. = 90°, time = 1h				
[PDMY] ^a				
0.23	6.21	7.1	0.20	
0.46	8.46	8.07	0.18	
0.69	9.99	9.86	—	
0.93	14.4	11.2	0.16	+45°
2.3	17.1	13.4		
3.4	20.97	17.9		
[MA] ^b				
0.55	5.85	3.8	—	—
0.925	14.4	11.2	—	+45°
1.295	15.5	17.8	—	—
1.48	19.8	20.5	—	—
[AN] ^c				
0.76	8.5	4.74	—	—
1.26	14.4	11.2	—	+45°
1.52	15.7	13.7	—	—
1.77	15.8	17.6	—	—
[LM] ^d				
0.51	14.4	11.2	—	+45°
0.62	10.8	9.3	—	+70°
0.73	10.4	8.7	—	+75°
0.83	8.41	8.0	—	+78°

^a[MA] = 0.51 mol dm⁻³, [AN] = 1.26 mol dm⁻³, [LM] = 0.92 mol dm⁻³.

^b[PDMY] = 0.93×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [LM] = 0.926 mol dm⁻³, [AN] = 1.26 mol dm⁻³. ^c[PDMY] = 0.93×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [MA] = 0.51 mol dm⁻³, [MA] = 0.926 mol dm⁻³. ^d[PDMY] = 0.93×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [MA] = 0.51 mol dm⁻³, [LM] = 0.926 mol dm⁻³.

Terpolymerization runs are associated with short induction periods of 5–7 min (Fig. 1). It is clear from Table 1 that R_p increases with [PDMY], [MA] and [AN]. However, it decreases with increase in [limonene]. The order of reaction with respect to [initiator] calculated from the slope of the linear plot of $\log R_p$ vs \log [PDMY], is 0.5, whereas the order of reaction with respect to [monomer], calculated from the slope of the linear plot of $\log R_p$ vs \log [monomer] is 1.12, 1.13 and (-1.31) for AN, MA and limonene respec-

tively, showing non-ideality for the polymerization systems. Various explanations for non-ideality³ have been proposed and now it has been accepted that primary radical termination and degradative chain transfer are the most important causes of non-ideality⁴.

The rate of polymerization was found to increase with the increase in temperature and the activation energy calculated from an Arrhenius plot has the value 77 kJ mol⁻¹.

The terpolymers were found to be soluble in dioxane and dimethylformamide and partially soluble in benzene and toluene : ν_{\max} 1740 (COOCH₃ of MA), 2310 (C=N of AN), 1350 (C-H bending of CH₃), 2940 (C-H) cm⁻¹; pmr δ 0.1-0.98 (CH₃ of limonene), 1.5-2.18 (CH, CH₂ of AN and MA). Viscosity of the terpolymers varied from 0.20 to 0.16 dl/g at 32 ± 0.1° (Table 1). Optical rotation varied from ±45 to ±78° depending on the terpolymer composition.

It may be concluded that pyridiniumdicyanomethylide can be used to synthesize optically active terpolymer of methyl acrylate, acrylonitrile and limonene.

Experimental

Methyl acrylate and acrylonitrile were purified by standard methods⁵. Limonene, tetracyanoethylene oxide (Fluka) and pyridine (E. Merck) were used as received. The purity of terpolymers was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A (100 MHz) instrument using TMS as an internal standard. The intrinsic viscosity (η_{int}) was determined in dioxane using an Ubbelohde viscometer at 32 ± 0.1°. The thermal

stability was determined using a TG-750 instrument. Optical rotation was measured with a polarimeter (cell length 10 cm, temp. 32°, 0.03 g terpolymer in 1 ml of dimethylformamide).

The pyridinium dicyanomethylide (PDMY) was prepared by the reported method⁶.

Synthesis of terpolymer. A solution containing monomers and PDMY in dimethylformamide was introduced into a dilatometer and polymerization was carried out for 1 h at 90 ± 0.1° under nitrogen atmosphere. The terpolymer was precipitated into distilled water and dried to constant weight.

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